

Epidemic Engines: A Study of the Factors Driving HIV Infection Spread and Mortality in the Regions of the Russian Federation

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Abstract

This paper examines the socio-economic determinants of the HIV epidemic in Russian regions, focusing on morbidity and mortality rates. It addresses the following questions: What factors contribute to the development of the HIV epidemic in Russia's regions? Which of these factors have the greatest impact on HIV-related morbidity and mortality?

The study employs the principal component analysis method to reduce dimensionality and identify grouped factors. The analysis is based on extended data from HIV Infection Monitoring Form No. 61 for the years 2012–2019. As a result, ten socio-economic determinants were identified, and their statistical relationship with HIV morbidity and mortality was assessed. A significant association was found between morbidity and mortality rates and factors such as population mobility and access to antiretroviral therapy (ART), similar to patterns observed in other countries experiencing an active HIV epidemic.

Keywords

HIV, economic effects, epidemic, factor analysis, social policy assessment, GRP, mortality, morbidity

JEL codes: I18, I15, J18

Introduction

This article examines the factors influencing the spread of HIV and related diseases across Russian regions.

One of the first recorded deaths in the USSR from acquired immunodeficiency syndrome (AIDS) occurred in 1985, shortly after Luc Montagnier's group at the Pasteur Institute

(France) isolated a new retrovirus in 1983. Initially, cases of the disease were reported only among international students from Africa (South Africa, Cameroon, etc.). However, the infection soon took root in the general population and began to spread.

Today, HIV infection has become a socially significant public health issue, with the number of infected individuals in Russia exceeding one million (Pokrovsky et al. 2017). In other words, the situation can be classified as an HIV epidemic. As a key determinant of societal well-being, public health – critical for maintaining workforce productivity – is severely undermined by the infection, leading to economic losses (Farmer 1999).

The first study to acknowledge HIV-related losses and attempt to assess the economic impact of public health deterioration due to HIV in Russia was conducted in the early 2000s (Prokhorov and Shmakov 2002). However, it provided only general estimates of disability and temporary work incapacity losses without detailing their underlying causes. Therefore, assessing the economic losses associated with the spread of HIV through an econometric analysis of mortality and morbidity in the Russian Federation remains a pressing and promising area of research.

Any economic and demographic study of infectious diseases must begin with an analysis of the factors driving their spread. Identifying and categorizing the determinants of HIV transmission in Russia, as well as those of other significant infections, presents considerable challenges. For instance, the respondent-driven sampling (RDS) methodology for control group allocation (Moran et al. 2020) is not applicable due to the need for extensive field research across various regions and the medical testing of respondents. Such studies require coordination with the Ministry of Health of the Russian Federation and regional regulatory authorities. Similarly, the use of quasi-experimental methods is complicated (Lachaud 2007), as the available data panels and research process do not allow for a clear distinction between the treatment and control groups.

Based on this, my study poses the following research question: What factors determine the incidence and mortality rates of HIV infection across the regions of the Russian Federation?

Previous research suggests that morbidity per 100,000 population – and consequently, mortality – is higher in regions with a greater concentration of crowded transportation hubs, such as ports, airports, and major train stations (Padian et al. 2008). Additionally, it can be hypothesized that the likelihood of HIV infection increases in economically disadvantaged regions with lower levels of human capital. Indicators such as average income and the proportion of the population with higher education may play a significant role in shaping regional disparities in HIV prevalence.

Determinants of HIV Infection and Its Impact on Economic Well-Being

The study of HIV/AIDS and epidemics in general is a relatively new field in the academic literature, emerging in the 1970s. Most research in this area has focused on medical aspects, including pathogenesis, diagnosis, treatment, and prevention of HIV and other infectious diseases. The economic analysis of epidemics, however, has only gained traction more recently, with the first significant studies appearing in the late 1990s.

In these works, researchers examine the economic dimensions of epidemics, such as healthcare expenditures, labor force losses, and the costs associated with prevention and

control measures (Cuddington et al. 1994; Lamontagne et al. 2019). This field of study is rapidly expanding and has become a crucial tool for informing policy decisions and planning epidemic response strategies.

Biological and Social Causes of HIV Spread

A fundamental question for economists studying infectious diseases is identifying the key determinants of morbidity. To address this, we turn to research examining the spread of HIV in different countries.

Starting with the medical perspective, Perrin et al. (2003) investigate the dynamics of HIV transmission and the detection of various genetic variants of the virus in relation to global travel patterns. Given the relatively low genetic variability of HIV, such studies are particularly valuable for constructing a socio-demographic profile of potential super-spreaders. The study also explores the primary transmission channels. In Northern Europe and Russia, intravenous drug use is identified as the dominant factor in HIV transmission. On a global scale, sex tourism to Southeast Asian countries plays a significant role. Additionally, previous research has confirmed the impact of military conflicts on the spread of specific HIV strains in Africa and beyond.

Advancements in medical statistics have encouraged economists to analyze the socio-economic drivers of the HIV epidemic, further facilitated by access to quasi-experimental and field studies in African HIV outbreaks. For example, Padian et al. (2008), drawing on data from the 2013 UNAIDS report, examined the factors contributing to the spread of the disease across the African continent. This study was among the first to propose key mechanisms of HIV transmission.

The research highlights the role of civil wars in the postcolonial period and the population displacement caused by prolonged armed conflicts as significant contributors to the epidemic. Additionally, certain household and family practices prevalent in tropical Africa have been identified as factors that entrench the virus within the population. These include unprotected sexual activity, inadequate hygiene practices during wound care, and the prevalence of domestic violence against women. Combined with rapid urbanization, these factors have led to an explosive increase in HIV incidence in the region.

This topic has been further explored in a range of classification studies, such as those by Moran et al. (2020) and Lachaud (2007). These studies, based on survey data, quasi-experimental approaches, and macroeconomic and demographic statistics, identify statistically significant determinants of HIV incidence.

Of particular interest is the role of socio-geographical factors. For instance, Lachaud (2007) examines the structural influence of cultural affiliation within the geographical context of social practices and human capital. Moran et al. (2020), building on an established methodological framework, assess the contribution of homosexual contacts to the spread of HIV in Côte d'Ivoire. Their findings suggest that traditional methods of targeting high-risk groups may no longer be effective in influencing epidemic dynamics.

Russia has a well-developed network of state AIDS centers and a substantial body of official medical statistics on the spread of HIV. In a review article by Sokolova et al. (2013), the primary transmission channels of HIV are identified as homosexual and heterosexual contacts, vertical transmission (from mother to child), and intravenous drug use. The study

highlights gender-based differences in transmission routes: intravenous drug use is more prevalent among men (accounting for 77.6% of cases), whereas heterosexual transmission is the dominant mode among women. Based on these findings, the authors conclude that HIV exhibits a pattern of diffuse transmission within couples. A similar trend was observed in a subsequent study by Pokrovsky et al. (2017).

Russian demographers, like their international counterparts, study the social determinants of the HIV epidemic. In an article by Aghajanyan and Zotova (2014), a model of HIV transmission among migrant workers is developed based on surveys of men and women from Central Asian communities and demographic statistics. The study assesses the causal relationship between infection risk and cultural and living conditions, concluding that the better a migrant is integrated into the socio-cultural environment of the Russian Federation, the lower their risk of infection. This article is particularly notable for its integration of econometric survey data analysis, medical statistics, and quasi-experimental methods for risk assessment.

Thus, HIV emerges as a significant chronic infectious disease with both social and household transmission pathways. However, due to its immunosuppressive nature, HIV inevitably facilitates the onset of other infectious diseases. The literature particularly highlights the role of tuberculosis and hepatitis in contributing to disability and mortality among individuals with HIV, which in turn affects quality of life, labor productivity, and workforce attrition. Given these implications, the continued spread of HIV warrants further attention from an economic perspective.

The damage caused by HIV infection and ways to overcome it

The HIV epidemic is severely impacting the well-being of regions, and as established earlier, this decline in public health is directly linked to rising morbidity and mortality. Below, we will describe some of the mechanisms through which HIV interacts with socio-economic determinants of development.

In a study by Lamontagne et al. (2019), the authors analyze the economic benefits of implementing a strategy to end the HIV/AIDS epidemic by 2030. They assess the long-term economic consequences of the epidemic by considering various investment scenarios for HIV/AIDS prevention and treatment and their impact on key indicators such as GDP, investment, consumption, and labor productivity.

The authors conclude that ending the HIV/AIDS epidemic as a public health threat would yield significant economic benefits at both the national and international levels. They argue that investments in HIV/AIDS prevention and treatment are economically viable and can deliver both short- and long-term benefits, including GDP growth, improved labor productivity, and reduced healthcare costs.

The primary research on HIV infection in Russia includes an influential article by Pokrovsky et al. (2017), a leading expert in the field. In this work, the author systematizes data on morbidity and mortality, evaluating the effectiveness of measures implemented in the Russian Federation from the perspective of an epidemiologist.

Additionally, the article by Prokhorov and Shmakov (2002) introduces a methodology for assessing the economic damage caused by temporary disability and permanent disability. This methodology is based on labor productivity characteristics, the likelihood of acquiring certain attributes of human capital, and government measures to support healthcare.

Collectively, these works provide a framework for assessing the potential economic damage resulting from HIV infection.

When considering Russian approaches to the study of morbidity and public health, it is essential to highlight the cartographic school of V.S. Tikunov (Prokhorov and Tikunov 2005). In their joint article, Prokhorov and Tikunov (2005) develop a medical and demographic classification of Russian regions based on a public health criterion they introduced. The authors justify the relevance of this indicator as an integral measure, combining life expectancy and infant mortality. This approach allows for an assessment of regional health conditions and supports the development of a socially and geographically based classification of Russian regions. The study identifies the most problematic areas, such as Khakassia, Buryatia, and the Chita Oblast, among others. Based on this classification, the authors also adjust their forecasts for life expectancy in these regions.

In an article by Podymova et al. (2018), the authors analyze the socio-economic impact of HIV infection in the Sverdlovsk Oblast using statistical data and correlation analysis. Drawing on data from the AIDS Center of the Sverdlovsk Oblast, they calculate the DALY (Disability-Adjusted Life Years) indicators for HIV patients and conduct a comprehensive cost analysis of the lives of these individuals. The authors also examine how social determinants have reduced the reproductive function of HIV-positive women.

The article discusses several strategies to mitigate the negative impact of HIV on both the economy and society, including increasing testing coverage, targeting at-risk groups, and combating discrimination against HIV-positive individuals.

Building on the insights from these studies, I will analyze the key factors driving the HIV epidemic. From this analysis, it will become evident which measures can help prevent the further spread of HIV and guide the development of an empirical strategy for the macroeconomic assessment of the epidemic's losses.

Data

To conduct the necessary analysis, it was essential to first create a comprehensive database encompassing the incidence of HIV infection, medical care for patients, mortality, and socio-economic indicators at the regional level across Russia over a defined period. The data structure used is a panel format.

For the creation of this database, we utilized statistical indicators from Form No. 61 “HIV Infection Monitoring” (Monitoring the spread of HIV infection in the subjects of the Russian Federation 2020), completed by the Ministry of Health of the Russian Federation, as well as statistical data from Form C52, which reports the number of deaths by cause. Additionally, socio-economic characteristics of Russian regions were sourced from the Federal State Statistics Service of the Russian Federation, aggregated within the EMISS system and the ENID platform.

The advantage of this dataset lies in the breadth of its indicators, ranging from the population's coverage of HIV testing to the number of infectious disease doctors per capita, from income per capita to the incidence of car accidents per 100,000 people. However, a notable disadvantage is the incompleteness of the data compared to Western standards. Specifically, there is a lack of detailed information on the deceased and infected populations by employment status and other social indicators, as well as insufficient data on monitoring and targeting key risk groups.

Data on the regions of Russia were collected from 2012 to 2019, thus excluding the impact of the coronacrisis and the 2008-2010 financial crisis from the analysis. During this period, the size of the dataset expanded following the annexation of the Republic of Crimea and the city of Sevastopol in 2014. Additionally, in 2018, the composition of the Siberian and Far Eastern Federal Districts was altered. However, since the analysis does not rely on data from federal districts, and the gaps for the new subjects of the Federation were filled using data from the State Statistics Service of Ukraine, it can be assumed that no significant informational shocks occurred to impede the study.

Methods

To analyze the relationship between socio-economic determinants and morbidity and mortality, it is essential to first address the issue of having an excessive number of determinants relative to the number of observations. Additionally, it is important to explore how, based on the internal structure of the dataset, the regressors relate not only to the dependent variable but also to one another. To achieve this, I focus on the principal component modification method for panel data.

This approach has been employed in studies such as Carreño et al. (2022), where categorical principal component analysis (CATPCA) was used to examine risk factors for nosocomial infections in patients with acute heart disease. In their study, the authors developed two models with two components each to assess the relationship between hospital-acquired infections (HAIs) and diagnostic categories (DCs) in these patients. The first model included all cases, while the second focused exclusively on cases involving HAIs. In both models, the first component was predominantly explained by the duration of invasive device use, the length of stay in intensive care, and the APACHE II score (a severity assessment of the patient's condition). The second component was associated with the type of hospitalization and diagnostic categories. Both models effectively highlighted the importance of factors related to the patient's initial health in shaping the risk of hospital-acquired infections, using panel data with intragroup transformation.

Another relevant example is the study by Yang et al. (2010), which models longevity risks using the principal component method on panel data and compares this approach with existing stochastic mortality models. The proposed PCA model was compared with well-known models such as the Lee-Carter model and the age – period – generation (APC) model. The PCA model demonstrated lower forecast errors for most of the countries examined, in comparison to the established models.

Building on these studies, I have developed the following empirical work strategy:

1. Perform an in-group transformation for the dataset. If necessary, exclude variables that exhibit no variation.
2. Apply principal component analysis (PCA) with equamax rotation (an orthogonal rotation method tied to the dimensionality of the dataset) to the transformed dataset.
3. Construct linear regressions using the principal components to analyze HIV morbidity and mortality from HIV-related diseases.

This approach will result in a panel model with identified principal components and bidirectional fixed effects, enabling the control of unobservable individual characteristics of regions and time periods in the simulation results.

Empirical results

I will begin by analyzing the determinants of HIV morbidity and mortality, with the aim of comparing these factors to those explored in studies from other countries. The dependent variables for this analysis are as follows:

- HIV incidence per 100.000 people (the number of people diagnosed for the first time);
- Mortality from HIV-related diseases, disaggregated by urban and rural areas, per 100.000 people.

The dataset contains numerous variables (see Table 1), some of which exhibit correlations with each other (see Figure 1). A detailed description of these variables can be found in Ap-

Table 1. Descriptive statistics of the dataset

Statistic	N	Mean	St. Dev.	Min	Max
Year	680	2.015.500	2.293	2.012	2.019
hiv_therapy_regdispensaries	680	51.862	19.011	0.000	107.300
hiv_regdispensaries_numdetect	680	72.500	17.281	19.900	109.600
hiv_firstdiagnosis_100k	680	49.100	38.979	0.000	239.800
hiv_motherchild_chemoprophylaxis	680	88.474	9.796	0.000	106.400
per_infectious_inalldoctors	680	1.108	0.289	0.500	2.300
rural_100k	680	6.077	7.813	0.000	57.799
urban_100k	680	9.267	10.575	0.000	67.004
Migration	680	-5.511	60.000	-223.000	439.000
Unemployment	680	10.271	11.934	0.300	166.300
Income	680	27.191.550	11.902.100	10.190.000	83.385.000
Teacher	680	12.566	10.370	0.500	62.000
Mobile	680	1.764.517	341.834	20.600	3.188.800
GRP	680	502.155.800	759.426.400	77.877.200	7.527,837.000
Consumption	680	271.260.900	97.283.840	79.020.000	781.147.200
Population	680	1.726.391	1.759.952	43.000	12.678.000
Employees	680	853.731	1.070.664	31.300	8.875.100
Investments	680	137.280.100	276.520.400	8.758.000	2.625,864.000
Port	680	0.153	0.360	0	1
Travel	680	0.324	0.468	0	1
Million	680	0.224	0.417	0	1
Medplaces	680	273.882	53.392	113.000	507.600
dtp_100k	680	135.101	40.221	15.700	249.800
hiv_foreign_test	680	10.494.250	24.608.420	0.000	263.191.600
hiv_russian_test	680	438.344.100	1.076.816.000	7.117.438	11.557.117.000
num_alldoctors_100k	680	481.329.000	128.269.800	262.867.900	1.365.800.000

pendix 1. To address the issue of dimensionality and to group related factors, we will apply the principal component analysis (PCA) method.

After performing the intragroup transformation of the data, the variables related to the presence of a port and the presence of a million-plus city (i.e., “port” and “million”) were excluded from the analysis due to the lack of variation (the intragroup transformation resulted in these variables being reduced to zero).

To reduce dimensionality, we will apply the principal component method using the R statistical package (version 4.4.0) and the JetBrains DataSpell v1.2024 programming environment. In constructing a linear regression model for HIV mortality, disaggregated by rural and urban populations, we exclude the mortality rate variables (urban_100k, rural_100k) from the factor analysis to avoid redundancy.

To assess the suitability of the principal component method, we performed two tests: the Bartlett sphericity test and the Kaiser – Meyer – Olkin (KMO) measure (factor loadings are provided in Appendix 4). The P-value for the Bartlett test is 3.145e-10, indicating that the

Figure 1. Correlation matrix of variables

hypothesis of equal variances between groups is rejected. The KMO coefficient is 0.72, which suggests that the data is suitable for factor analysis.

The table of factor loadings can be found in Appendices 4 and 5.

Based on the eigenvalue criterion (>1) and the “rocky scree” plot (shown in Appendix 3), 10 factors were selected, which together account for 84% of the variance in the sample. The factor loadings are provided in Appendix 4.

The factors for mortality analysis, as outlined in Appendix 4, will be interpreted as follows: A significant contribution is considered to be a factor loading with a coefficient greater than 0.7 (or 0.5 in cases where no dominant variable is present within the component), in absolute value.

- Factor 1 “Socio-economic well-being and dispensary accounting” includes the following significant loads: *hiv_therapy_regdispensaries* (0.756), *income* (0.653), *consumption* (0.715), *age* (0.701). High values of this factor are associated with regions exhibiting elevated levels of income, consumption, a larger proportion of elderly individuals, and high coverage of antiretroviral therapy (ART).
- Factor 2 “HIV testing indicators” includes two significant loads: *hiv_foreign_test* (0.988), *hiv_russian_test* (0.983). High values of this factor indicate regions with active HIV testing initiatives for both Russian and foreign citizens. This enhanced testing contributes to better HIV detection and treatment, potentially leading to reduced mortality from HIV-related illnesses.
- Factor 3 “Mobile communications and population density” includes the following significant loads: *mobile* (0.631), *density* (0.831). High values of this factor are linked to regions with well-developed and high population density.
- Factor 4 “Proportion of infectious diseases doctors” includes the following significant loads: *per_infectious_inalldoctors* (0.844). High values of this factor reflect regions with a higher proportion of infectious disease specialists among all medical professionals. This is likely to improve the diagnosis and treatment of HIV, potentially reducing mortality rates associated with the disease.
- Factor 5 “Employment” includes *employees* (0.893). High values of this factor are associated with regions exhibiting high levels of employment and economic activity.
- Factor 6 “Unemployment rate” includes only *unemployment* (-0.599). High values of this factor are linked to regions with higher unemployment rates. Elevated unemployment can negatively affect access to healthcare services and other essential resources, leading to higher mortality from HIV-related illnesses.
- Factor 7 “Economic development and investments” includes the following significant loads: *GRP* (0.829), *investments* (0.888). High values of this factor are associated with regions with robust economic development, reflected in high gross regional product (GRP) and substantial investments.
- Factor 8 “Chemoprophylaxis of mothers and children” contains *hiv_motherchild_chemoprophylaxis* (-0.765). High values of this factor are associated with regions where active chemoprophylaxis programs are in place, aimed at reducing the transmission of HIV from mother to child. These programs are crucial in preventing new HIV infections in newborns, thereby contributing to a decrease in HIV-related mortality.
- Factor 9 “Tourism” contains *travel* (0.903). High values of this factor indicate regions with significant tourism activity, often with well-established tourist destinations.

- Factor 10 “Teacher availability” contains the teacher variable (0.761). High values of this factor are linked to regions with a high number of teachers per capita. This factor can serve as a proxy for access to verified information, as teachers are often key figures in spreading knowledge about health issues, including HIV prevention. Regions with more teachers may have better education systems, potentially improving public awareness about HIV and access to related health services.

It is important to note that these factors (ART, population mobility, access to information through teachers, and socio-economic well-being) are consistent with the findings from the first part of the literature review. After identifying and interpreting the factors, we will analyze the relationship between HIV mortality rates in the regions and the identified factors through regression analysis under reduced dimensionality conditions.

Let’s build a linear regression of variables *rural_100k* and *urban_100k* from the factors *I* discovered using the least squares method (OLS).

$$rural_{100k} = F * \hat{\beta} + const,$$

$$urban_{100k} = F * \hat{\beta} + const,$$

where *F* is the vector of factors, and $\hat{\beta}$ is the vector of coefficients for variables.

Table 2 presents the results of models using the principal component method for two dependent variables: *urban_100k* (model 1) and *rural_100k* (model 2). Based on the model results, we can conclude that the significant factors negatively associated with HIV mortality in urban and rural areas (*urban_100k* and *rural_100k*) include prevention coverage for mother – child couples, mobile communications and population density, employment, and the proportion of infectious disease specialists. These findings are consistent with previous studies (Padian et al. 2008; Lachaud 2007). A positive association with mortality was found for factors such as well-being, economic development, test coverage (specifically for rural areas), and teacher availability.

Thus, a positive coefficient for the well-being factor is associated with the inclusion of an age variable, which may reflect the age structure, specifically an older population, and the fact that wealthier regions tend to have more accurate death registrations. It is also expected that increased coverage of chemoprophylaxis for mother – child couples and a higher proportion of infectious disease specialists contribute to reducing HIV mortality. Interestingly, both employment and the composite factor of connectivity and population density show a negative relationship with HIV mortality. In the first case, this may indicate better access to high-quality medical care for the employed population, who are more likely to undergo professional health examinations and may have better awareness of HIV. In the second case, it could indicate more developed social infrastructure and better access to information in more densely populated areas.

In the model, teacher availability is positively associated with mortality, which may reflect better death registration in regions with greater access to education. Overall, the results obtained align with the conclusions of previous studies conducted in other countries, as well as with theoretical assumptions.

Now let’s apply the same methods to the variable *hiv_firstdiagnosis_100k* (incidence per hundred thousand population). The matrix of factor loadings can be found in Appendix 5. Let’s interpret the obtained factors.

- Factor 1 “Socio-economic well-being and age” includes the variables *income*, *consumption*, *age*, *migr_obr* (migration turnover), which reflect socio-economic well-be-

ing and the demographic characteristics of the population. High values of this factor indicate regions with higher income levels, greater consumption, a larger proportion of the elderly population, and active migration. These regions may face a higher risk of HIV transmission, as economic well-being could contribute to better HIV diagnosis and record-keeping.

- Factor 2 “Connectivity and population density” includes the variables mobile (mobile communications) and density (population density). This factor reflects the level of in-

Table 2. Specification of mortality models using the principal component method

	Dependent variable	
	urban_100k	rural_100k
	(1)	(2)
Welfare and dispensary accounting	1.827*** (0.140)	1.840*** (0.131)
Economic development and investments	0.490*** (0.140)	0.562*** (0.131)
HIV testing	0.046 (0.140)	0.415*** (0.131)
Mobile communications and population density	-0.546*** (0.140)	-0.402*** (0.131)
Employment	-0.341** (0.140)	-0.330** (0.131)
Tourism	0.028 (0.140)	0.239* (0.131)
Chemoprophylaxis of mother – child couples	-0.425*** (0.140)	-0.603*** (0.131)
Infectious diseases doctors	-0.653*** (0.140)	-0.270** (0.131)
Teacher availability	0.686*** (0.140)	0.424*** (0.131)
Unemployment	0.229 (0.140)	0.239* (0.131)
Constant	0.000 (0.140)	-0.000 (0.131)
Observations	680	680
R2	0.280	0.297
Adjusted R2	0.269	0.287
Residual Std. Error (df = 669)	3.660	3.420
F Statistic (df = 10; 669)	25.978***	28.277***

Note: * $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$.

frastructure and population density in a region. High values of this factor are associated with better infrastructure and higher population density, which can enhance access to healthcare services and improve the effectiveness of HIV detection and treatment.

- Factor 3 “HIV testing rates” includes the variables `hiv_foreign_test` and `hiv_russian_test`. This factor reflects the rates of HIV testing. High values of this factor indicate active HIV testing among both Russian and foreign citizens, which improves the detection and registration of HIV infections.
- Factor 4 “Availability of Doctors” includes the variable `num_alldoctors_100k`. This factor reflects the availability of doctors. High values of this factor indicate a higher number of doctors across all specialties per 100.000 population, which enhances the accessibility of medical services and supports more effective HIV treatment.
- Factor 5 “Chemoprophylaxis of mothers and children” includes `hiv_motherchild_chemoprophylaxis`. This factor represents the coverage of mother – child ART pairs. High values of this factor indicate the active use of chemoprophylaxis to prevent mother-to-child transmission of HIV, which helps reduce the number of new HIV cases.
- Factor 6 “Education and tourism” includes the variables `teacher` and `travel`. High values of this factor are associated with a strong educational infrastructure and the presence of tourist facilities, which can positively impact public awareness of HIV.
- Factor 7 “Economic development and investments” includes variables `GRP` and `investments`. This factor reflects economic development and the level of investment in a region. High values of this factor indicate regions with strong economic growth and significant investments, which can enhance healthcare infrastructure and improve HIV detection and treatment.
- Factor 8 “HIV mortality in urban and rural areas” includes variables `rural_100k` and `urban_100k`, reflecting HIV mortality rates in both urban and rural areas. High values of this factor indicate regions with elevated HIV mortality, which could be attributed to insufficient access to medical services or low levels of prevention and treatment.
- Factor 9 “HIV registration” includes the `hiv_regdispensaries_numdetect` variable. This factor represents the diagnosis and registration of HIV-infected individuals. High values of this factor indicate effective systems for registering HIV-infected people, which contributes to better monitoring and management of the epidemic.
- Factor 10 “Infectious Disease Specialists” includes the `per_infectious_inalldoctors` variable. This factor reflects the availability of medical personnel. High values of this factor indicate a higher proportion of infectious disease specialists, which contributes to more effective detection and treatment of HIV infections.

These factors provide insight into the main trends and relationships within HIV incidence data, which is valuable for developing targeted health and social policy measures. With this understanding, a panel linear regression on morbidity with fixed effects can now be constructed.

As observed from the model specification, 5 out of the 10 main components are significant. The components “Socio-economic well-being and age,” “HIV testing indicators,” and “Infectious disease specialists” all contribute positively to the incidence of HIV, which aligns with findings in the literature. High values of the first component, “Socio-economic well-being and age,” suggest that regions with higher income, consumption, a larger proportion of the elderly population, and active migration may experience better diagnosis and

reporting of HIV cases. The positive contribution of the “HIV testing indicators” component highlights that active HIV testing among the population leads to better detection and registration of HIV cases. The “Infectious disease specialists” component emphasizes the importance of having a sufficient number of infectious disease doctors for more effective detection and treatment of HIV cases.

At the same time, the following components make a significant negative contribution to HIV morbidity: “Chemoprophylaxis of mothers and children” and “Availability of doc-

Table 3. Specification of the HIV incidence model with the principal component method

	Dependent variable hiv_firstdiagnosis_100k
Welfare	2.487*** (0.481)
Mortality	-0.171 (0.481)
Economic development and investments	0.096 (0.481)
HIV testing	2.441*** (0.481)
Connectivity and population density	-0.417 (0.481)
Proportion of infectious diseases	0.841* (0.481)
Chemoprophylaxis of mother – child couples	-1.352*** (0.481)
Availability of doctors	-1.556*** (0.481)
Medical check-up	-1.278 (0.481)
Education and tourism	0.595 (0.481)
Constant	0.000 (0.480)
Observations	680
R ²	0.111
Adjusted R ²	0.098
Residual Std. Error	12.522 (df = 669)
F Statistic	8.357*** (df = 10; 669)

Note: * $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$.

tors.” The active use of chemoprophylaxis to prevent mother-to-child transmission of HIV reduces the number of new HIV cases, which explains the negative contribution of this component. Similarly, the high availability of doctors across all specialties per 100,000 population improves access to medical services and facilitates more effective HIV treatment, which in turn reduces morbidity.

On the other hand, the components “HIV mortality” and “Economic development and investment” do not show a statistically significant effect on HIV incidence. This may be because mortality and economic development influence HIV incidence indirectly through other factors.

An interesting observation is the significant negative coefficient for the availability of doctors, coupled with a positive coefficient for the proportion of infectious disease specialists. This may reflect the response and adaptation of the healthcare system to the progressive HIV epidemic. Specifically, as the number of HIV cases and HIV-related diseases increases in a region, the proportion of infectious disease specialists in the medical workforce also rises. This is because the creation of new infection wards in healthcare facilities requires the hiring of additional specialists to manage the increasing number of cases.

Overall, the regression model reveals that socio-economic factors such as income, per capita consumption expenditure, and migration, along with testing rates and medical infrastructure, make a significant contribution to HIV incidence. Preventive measures, such as chemoprophylaxis for mothers and children, as well as effective registration and monitoring of HIV-infected individuals, are crucial in reducing the incidence of HIV. These findings align with the literature, emphasizing the importance of economic conditions, healthcare infrastructure, and preventive strategies in controlling HIV incidence.

Conclusion

Based on the analysis of the models, it can be concluded that significant factors negatively associated with HIV mortality rates in urban and rural areas (urban_100k and rural_100k) include prevention coverage for mother – child couples, the prevalence of mobile communications and population density, employment, and the proportion of infectious disease specialists. Conversely, economic development, test coverage (only in rural areas), and teacher availability are positively associated with the HIV-related death rate. These findings align with the literature (Padian et al. 2008; Lachaud 2007). In regions with high-quality medical care for HIV-infected individuals, a high level of economic development, and better public awareness, the likelihood of dying from HIV is lower due to greater access to treatment.

The positive coefficient for the welfare factor can be explained by the inclusion of the age variable. This may reflect changes in the age structure, as well as the accuracy of death cause registration in wealthier regions. It is also expected that chemoprophylaxis coverage for mother – child couples and the number of infectious disease specialists are statistically associated with lower HIV mortality. Interestingly, employment and the composite factor of mobile communications and population density are negatively associated with mortality rates. In the case of employment, this may indicate better access to quality medical care for employed individuals, who are more likely to undergo medical examinations as part of their professional checks, as well as higher awareness levels. In the case of population density and mobile communications, it could suggest

more developed social infrastructure and better access to health information in densely populated areas.

Teacher availability (a composite variable) is positively associated with mortality, which could also serve as a marker for better death registration in regions with better access to education (Padian et al. 2008). In such regions, deaths among HIV-infected individuals, especially in older age groups, are more accurately recorded.

Based on the morbidity model, five out of the ten components are significant. “Socio-economic well-being and age,” “HIV testing rates,” and “Infectious disease specialists” are positively associated with HIV incidence. High values of the first component indicate regions with high income and active migration, which are associated with better diagnosis and case reporting. The positive contribution of HIV testing emphasizes the importance of actively identifying HIV cases. The “Infectious disease specialists” component underscores the critical role of doctors in diagnosing and treating HIV infections.

The negative statistical contribution comes from the “Chemoprophylaxis of mothers and children” and “Availability of doctors” components. Chemoprophylaxis reduces the number of new HIV cases, while high availability of doctors enhances access to medical services. Components such as “HIV mortality in urban and rural areas” and “Economic development and investment,” which were found to be statistically insignificant, likely influence morbidity indirectly through other factors.

The HIV epidemic in Russia appears to be mature, as evidenced by the significant negative coefficient for the availability of doctors and the positive coefficient for the proportion of infectious disease specialists. This suggests that the healthcare system has adapted to the epidemic, with increasing numbers of infectious disease specialists responding to the rising HIV caseload.

The obtained model, though not perfect, provides valuable insight into the main trends and factors influencing the spread of the HIV epidemic in Russia between 2012 and 2019. An important factor driving the epidemic is the accumulated viral load within the population, which complicates efforts to control the disease for both government authorities and society at large. However, a more comprehensive analysis could be conducted if data on the estimated number of individuals in risk groups, as outlined in the UNAIDS 90-90-90 strategy (UNAIDS 2021), were available. The taboo surrounding this issue hampers efforts to reduce HIV transmission and limits research opportunities.

Due to the specific nature of the data – where all HIV-related measures have been implemented at the federal level since 2013 and applied uniformly across regions, yet with significant regional discrepancies in the reporting of morbidity and mortality – it is challenging to conduct causality tests. Therefore, the author leaves the determination of statistical relationships as the focus of the research.

The improvement of the information base appears to be promising, particularly through the addition of data on the age of death from the C51 forms, which would allow for a breakdown of deaths by age. However, these data should also be supplemented with information on morbidity by age, which is currently available only in limited circulation at the Federal State Budgetary Institution “TSNIIOIZ” under the Ministry of Health of the Russian Federation. Additionally, attention could be given to the creation or adaptation of a health well-being index at the regional level. This would provide a more accurate ranking of regions and an assessment of the geographical factors contributing to disparities, offering more advanced control variables and reliable proxies for analysis.

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Appendix 1

Table A1. Full description of the data set used

Name of the variable	Description	Type
hiv_therapy_regdispensaries	Proportion of HIV-infected people receiving antiretroviral therapy among those registered at the dispensary	num
hiv_regdispensaries_numdetect	The proportion of HIV-infected persons registered at the dispensary, out of the number of identified	num
hiv_firstdiagnosis_100k	Incidence of newly diagnosed HIV infection per 100.000 population	num
hiv_motherchild_chemoprophylaxis	Coverage of mother–child couples with chemoprophylaxis in accordance with current standards	num
hiv_russian_test	Number of Russian citizens with positive results of IB and ELISA tests for HIV antibodies per 1 billion people (for the reporting year)	num
hiv_foreign_test	Number of Russian citizens with positive results of IB and ELISA tests for HIV antibodies per 1 billion people (for the reporting year)	num
num_alldoctors_100k	Number of doctors of all specialties (individuals) in organizations providing medical services to the population per 1 billion people at the end of the reporting year.	num
per_infectious_inalldoctors	Share of infectious diseases doctors out of the total number of doctors of all specialties (individuals) in organizations providing medical services to the population at the end of the reporting year	num
Year	Reporting year	num
urban_100k	Mortality from human immunodeficiency virus disease per 100.000 population in urban areas	num

Name of the variable	Description	Type
rural_100k	Mortality from human immunodeficiency virus disease per 100.000 population in rural areas	num
Income	Average monthly income per capita, in rubles	num
Teacher	Number of teachers in primary, basic and secondary general education programmes in thousands	num
Migr_obr	Migration turnover by region	num
Mobile	Number of connected mobile subscriber devices per 1,000 population	num
Consumption	Consumer spending on average per capita in rubles, per month	num
Employees	Ratio of the working age population to the total population	num
Investments	Investments per capita, in rubles	num
Port	Presence of a large industrial port in the region	bool
Travel	Availability of a recreation center in the region	bool
Million	Presence of a million-plus city in the region	bool
Medplaces	Number of hospital beds per 10.000 population	num
Dtp_100k	Number of car accidents per 100.000 population	num
Density	Population density	num
Age	Average age of the population	num

Appendix 2

Table A2. Description of the data set provided by ANO “CAG” INID

Name of the variable	Description	Type
hiv_therapy_regdispensaries	Proportion of HIV-infected people receiving antiretroviral therapy among those registered at the dispensary	num
hiv_regdispensaries_numdetect	The proportion of HIV-infected persons registered at the dispensary, out of the number of identified	num
hiv_firstdiagnosis_100k	Incidence for the first time in life by established diagnosis of HIV infection per 100.000 population	num
hiv_motherchild_chemoprophylaxis	Coverage of mother – child couples with chemoprophylaxis in accordance with current standards	num
hiv_regnum_firstdiagnosis	Number of registered patients diagnosed with HIV infection for the first time in their lives	num
hiv_totalnumrussian_tested	Total number of Russian citizens tested for antibodies to HIV infection	num
hiv_russian_ibtestedpositive	Number of Russian citizens with positive results of IB tests for antibodies to HIV infection	num
hiv_russian_ifatedestedpositive	Number of Russian citizens with positive ELISA test results for HIV antibodies	num
hiv_totalnumforeign_tested	Total number of foreign citizens tested for antibodies to HIV infection	num

Name of the variable	Description	Type
hiv_foreign_ibtestedpositive	Number of foreign citizens with positive ELISA test results for HIV antibodies	num
hiv_foreign_ifatedestedpositive	Number of foreign citizens with positive ELISA test results for HIV antibodies	num
num_alldoctors_inmedorgservices	Number of doctors of all specialties (individuals) in organizations providing medical services to the population per 1 billion people at the end of the reporting year.	Num
num_infectiousdoctors_inmedorgservices	Number of doctors of all specialties (individuals) in organizations providing medical services to the population at the end of the reporting year.	num
per_infectious_inalldoctors	Share of infectious diseases doctors out of the total number of doctors of all specialties (individuals) in organizations providing medical services to the population at the end of the reporting year	num

Appendix 3

Charts of the “rocky scree” type from Appendices 4-5.

Figure A1. A graph of the “rocky scree” type for selecting the number of main components in the analysis of mortality from HIV-related disease

Figure A2. A graph of the “rocky scree” type for selecting the number of main components in the analysis of HIV incidence

Appendix 4

Table A3. Table of factor loads for mortality analysis

	mortalityFactors									
	PC1	PC2	PC3	PC4	PC5	PC6	PC7	PC8	PC9	PC10
hiv_therapy_regdispensaries	0.756	0.108	0.012	-0.111	-0.085	0.063	0.255	-0.024	0.092	0.202
hiv_regdispensaries_numdetect	-0.086	-0.029	-0.008	0.013	0.015	0.042	0.026	-0.033	-0.022	-0.236
hiv_firstdiagnosis_100k	0.078	0.189	-0.048	-0.088	-0.115	-0.269	-0.037	0.416	0.350	0.115
hiv_motherchild_chemoprophylaxis	0.190	-0.045	0.100	0.059	-0.309	-0.124	0.081	-0.765	0.112	0.040
per_infectious_inalldoctors	0.115	0.022	-0.301	0.844	0.077	-0.068	-0.070	-0.080	0.064	0.111
unemployment	-0.307	-0.043	0.120	-0.237	0.089	-0.599	0.058	0.027	0.095	0.235
income	0.653	0.156	0.030	-0.163	-0.031	0.005	0.472	-0.004	0.246	-0.156
teacher	-0.132	0.012	0.059	-0.180	0.040	0.007	0.011	0.042	0.259	0.761
mobile	0.285	0.003	0.631	-0.093	0.489	0.071	-0.097	-0.130	0.105	-0.065
GRP	0.184	0.197	0.089	-0.071	-0.051	0.113	0.829	-0.022	0.066	0.016
consumption	0.715	0.095	0.063	-0.138	-0.047	0.210	0.386	0.005	0.163	0.033
employees	-0.006	-0.008	-0.053	0.070	0.893	0.011	0.023	0.135	-0.035	0.009
investments	-0.039	0.079	0.028	-0.029	-0.015	-0.015	0.888	-0.071	0.0001	-0.001
travel	0.074	-0.023	0.005	0.042	-0.011	-0.026	0.013	-0.007	0.903	0.120
medplaces	0.447	-0.036	0.537	-0.068	-0.069	0.240	0.149	0.199	0.075	-0.115
dtp_100k	-0.565	-0.069	-0.023	0.291	0.138	-0.167	-0.176	-0.066	-0.159	0.046
hiv_foreign_test	0.007	0.988	-0.022	-0.012	-0.009	-0.020	0.077	0.050	0.008	0.00001
hiv_russian_test	0.035	0.983	-0.014	0.006	-0.013	-0.006	0.111	0.058	0.028	0.003
num_alldoctors_100k	0.006	0.004	0.246	0.431	-0.264	0.214	0.203	0.356	-0.168	0.178
density	-0.102	-0.007	0.831	-0.250	-0.173	-0.031	0.024	-0.107	0.009	0.030
age	0.701	0.114	-0.130	0.014	-0.172	0.204	0.228	0.054	0.115	0.083
migr_obr	0.383	0.108	-0.579	-0.131	-0.108	0.145	-0.185	-0.075	0.087	-0.135

Appendix 5

Table A4. Table of factor loadings for morbidity analysis

	PrevalenceFactors									
	RC1	RC2	RC3	RC4	RC5	RC6	RC7	RC8	RC9	RC10
hiv_therapy_regdispensaries	0.554	0.142	0.090	0.196	0.074	0.044	0.237	0.481	-0.445	-0.072
hiv_regdispensaries_numdetect	0.050	0.031	-0.027	0.082	0.007	-0.002	0.036	0.048	0.967	-0.005
hiv_motherchild_chemoprophylaxis	0.049	0.211	-0.088	-0.308	0.722	-0.036	0.152	0.116	0.067	0.241
per_infectious_inalldoctors	-0.001	-0.061	0.014	0.077	-0.010	-0.058	-0.049	-0.105	-0.003	0.833
rural_100k	0.144	0.017	0.099	-0.007	0.109	0.024	0.107	0.892	0.048	-0.009
urban_100k	0.125	-0.027	0.0004	-0.052	0.068	0.073	0.082	0.911	-0.002	-0.113
unemployment	-0.087	0.038	0.003	-0.425	-0.048	-0.259	0.052	-0.318	-0.124	-0.351
income	0.667	0.216	0.137	0.121	0.084	0.139	0.495	0.281	0.024	-0.077
teacher	-0.068	-0.017	-0.001	0.109	-0.042	0.770	-0.001	-0.034	0.038	-0.048
mobile	0.065	0.865	-0.023	-0.050	-0.160	0.026	-0.026	0.023	0.034	-0.013
GRP	0.198	0.081	0.188	0.139	0.078	0.043	0.832	0.095	0.050	-0.088
consumption	0.701	0.246	0.075	0.218	0.084	0.090	0.400	0.300	0.058	-0.075
employees	-0.037	0.265	-0.015	-0.211	-0.808	-0.011	0.058	-0.043	0.044	0.185
investments	-0.048	-0.035	0.077	0.062	0.019	-0.008	0.888	0.039	-0.019	-0.047
travel	0.098	0.066	0.008	-0.165	0.033	0.700	0.023	0.060	-0.073	-0.026
medplaces	0.304	0.475	-0.020	0.419	0.049	-0.047	0.127	0.056	0.091	-0.297
dtp_100k	-0.580	-0.072	-0.071	-0.114	-0.085	-0.059	-0.167	-0.259	-0.041	0.292
hiv_foreign_test	0.022	-0.018	0.990	0.007	-0.015	-0.0002	0.072	0.047	-0.026	-0.006
hiv_russian_test	0.061	-0.007	0.986	0.032	-0.012	0.016	0.106	0.017	-0.024	0.003
num_alldoctors_100k	-0.043	0.011	0.028	0.777	0.017	-0.020	0.129	-0.172	0.123	0.079
density	-0.260	0.598	-0.008	0.177	0.358	0.067	0.039	-0.174	-0.047	-0.365
age	0.653	0.018	0.101	0.315	0.093	0.058	0.214	0.396	0.062	0.022
migr_obr	0.714	-0.353	0.098	-0.261	0.075	-0.015	-0.168	0.039	0.072	0.081